

An uncommon 14-Methyldihydroxy Steroid from the Soft Coral *Nephthea chabroli* of Indian Coast¹

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The ethyl acetate extract of the soft coral *Nephthea chabroli* furnished a new 14-methyldihydroxy steroid whose structure was established as 14 α ,24(S)-dimethylcholestan-3 β ,25-diol (**1a**) by a study of its spectral data.

Soft corals (Phylum : Coelenterata) are a rich source of various sesqui- and diterpenoids, and polyoxygenated steroids with multiple functionalities¹. Recently, we have reported the isolation of four new sesquiterpenoids and two diterpenoids from the ethyl acetate extract of the soft coral *Nephthea chabroli*² collected from the Mandapam (W9°16', E79°12') coast of the South-Eastern part of Indian peninsula³. We wish to report herein the isolation of a new minor sterol from the same extract, and elucidation of its structure as 14 α ,24(S)-dimethylcholestan-3 β ,25-diol (**1a**) by a study of its physical and spectral data. This happens to be the first report of the presence of a 14-methyldihydroxysteroid from any marine organism. The initial aqueous extract of the soft coral *Nephthea chabroli* showed diuretic activity.

The residue from the CHCl₃-CH₃OH (8 : 2) fractions on crystallisation from CH₃OH-CHCl₃ (1 : 1) furnished the new sterol as colourless flakes (**1a**) m.p. 276-78°, [α]_D + 22.21° (c 0.65, CH₃OH). Its molecular formula was deduced as C₂₉H₅₂O₂ from its elemental analysis and EIMS molecular ion M⁺ 432, and it was transparent to uv above 210 nm. It exhibited a peak at 3500 cm⁻¹ for a hydroxyl in its ir spectrum. On acetylation (Ac₂O/Py), it gave a monoacetate (**1b**), C₃₁H₅₄O₃, m.p. 254-56°, [α]_D + 43.11° (c 0.83, CH₃OH) which showed the acetate carbonyl at 1725 cm⁻¹ as well as the hydroxylic

absorption at 3450 cm^{-1} in its ir spectrum. From this it was inferred that the new sterol is a dihydroxy compound with one acylable hydroxyl and the second a tertiary or hindered hydroxyl. The presence of two hydroxyls was evident by the peaks at δ 72.3 and 68.5 in its ^{13}C nmr spectrum. Its ^1H nmr spectrum showed three tertiary methyls at δ 0.66, 0.83 and 1.06 as singlets, two secondary methyls at δ 0.87 and 0.92 as doublets (J 6 Hz) in addition to two more methyls at δ 1.24 and 1.26 as singlets which were obviously assigned to the methyls connected to a carbon bearing an oxygen. This observation located the tertiary hydroxyl at C-25 in the side-chain. No olefinic protons were observed, showing its saturated nature. The only other proton that could be noticed at δ 3.85 as a multiplet ($W_{1/2}$ 15.5 Hz) was that of the usual $3\alpha\text{-H}$ over the β -hydroxyl of the steroid unit. In the absence of any olefinic proton, the steroid should necessarily be a saturated 3,25-dihydroxy compound. The prominent fragment ion at 289 ($M^+ - 143$, 65%) indicated the loss of $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}\text{O}$, the side-chain unit of the molecule **1a**. This side-chain could accommodate two secondary methyls at C-20 and C-24 as well as the two methyls connected to C-25 with a hydroxylic function attached to it. There remaining three more tertiary methyls, which include the C-18 and C-19 methyls. So, the third tertiary methyl might be located at C-14, C-8, C-9 or C-5. The ions of particular significance were at 246/186, 192/240, 166/266 cleaved as per steroid fragmentation (Scheme 1) on the lines (e), (d) and (c) which clearly showed the extra tertiary methyl at C-14 position. The ^{13}C nmr spectrum of **1a** was taken in both the off-resonance and proton decoupled modes. The configuration of 14-methyl was decided as α by comparing its ^{13}C nmr values of appropriate carbons with those of 14α -methylcholesterol⁴ (**2**) (Table 1). Similarly, a comparison of the ^{13}C nmr chemical shift values of the carbons present in the side-chain with those present in $24(\xi)$ -methylcholestan- $3\beta,5\alpha,6\beta,25$ -tetrol (**3**), the meta-

bolite isolated from *Lobophytum pauciflorum*⁵ confirmed their identical side-chains in both the

TABLE 1- ^{13}C NMR DATA FOR DIHYDROXYSTEROID (**1a**)

Position of carbon	Multiplicity	1a δ	2 δ	3 δ
C-1	t	37.2		
C-2	t	31.2		
C-3	d	68.5		
C-4	t	39.2		
C-5	d	44.1		
C-6	t	28.9		
C-7	t	32.5		
C-8	d	35.5	36.2	
C-9	d	43.5	43.1	
C-10	s	36.6	37.4	
C-11	t	20.8	20.1	
C-12	t	35.7	33.9	
C-13	s	47.5	47.5	
C-14	s	44.8	45.2	
C-15	t	26.9	27.0	
C-16	t	28.5	28.0	
C-17	d	56.5		
C-18	q	13.2		
C-19	q	13.5		
C-20	d	36.8		36.8
C-21	q	19.4		19.3
C-22	t	35.9		35.7
C-23	t	28.6		28.6
C-24	d	46.0		46.0
C-25	s	72.3		72.2
C-26	q	26.4		26.6
C-27	q	28.0		28.1
C-24 Methyl	q	15.3		15.1
C-14 Methyl	q	16.4	16.8	

molecules, leaving the stereochemistry at C-24 to be decided (*R* or *S*). For biogenetic considerations, the configuration of 24-methyl might be taken as (*S*)⁶. Hence the stereochemistry at C-24 in **1a** and **1b** has been taken as (*S*) as in other sterol congeners, reported in particular from soft corals. Thus the structure of the new sterol (**1a**) was proposed as 14 α ,24(*S*)-dimethylcholestan-3 β ,25-diol.

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